

Dual application of Ti-catalyzed Li-RHC composite for H₂ purification and CO methanation

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Figure S1 – Evolution of the hydrogen storage capacity with the cycle number for Li-RHC-Ti composite.

Figure S2 – XRPD patterns of the Li-RHC-Ti material after: (a) mechanical milling for 2 h (Li-RHC-Ti), (b) 10th dehydrogenation (with rehydrogenation under 5.0 MPa H₂) and (c) 10th dehydrogenation (with rehydrogenation 5.0 MPa CO-H₂).

MgH₂ + CO

Species	Initial composition (mol %)	Final composition under pure CO at 400 °C (mol %)
CO ₂ (g)		0.0
MgH ₂ (s)	66.66	1.0
MgO(s)		26.7
Mg(s)		25.7
C(s)		10.5
CH ₄ (g)		16.2
H ₂ (g)		19.9
CO(g)	33.33	0.0
H ₂ O(g)		0.0
O ₂ (g)		0.0
HCOO(g)		0.0
CH ₃ OH(g)		0.0
B(CH ₃) ₃ (g)		0.00

Table S1 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the MgH₂-CO interactions upon heating ramp from RT to 400 °C under pure CO atmosphere.

Figure S3 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the MgH_2 -CO interactions upon heating ramp from RT to 600 °C under pure CO atmosphere for the phases showing changes.

LiBH₄ + CO

Species	Initial composition (mol %)	Final composition under 0.27 MPa CO and at 400 °C (mol %)
CO ₂ (g)		0.0
C(s)		35.4
CH ₄ (g)		23.0
H ₂ (g)		12.4
CO(g)	66.66	0.0
LiBH ₄ (s)	33.33	0.0
LiBO ₂ (s)		29.2
LiH(s)		0.0
H ₂ O(g)		0.00
O ₂ (g)		0.00
HCOO(g)		0.00
CH ₃ OH(g)		0.00
BO ₂ (g)		0.00
B ₂ H ₆ (g)		0.00
B(CH ₃) ₃ (g)		0.00

Table S2 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the LiBH₄-CO interactions upon heating ramp from RT to 400 °C under pure CO atmosphere.

Figure S4 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the LiBH₄-CO interactions upon heating ramp from RT to 600 °C under pure CO atmosphere for the phases showing changes.

Li-RHC-Ti + CO

Species	Initial composition (mol %)	Final composition under 0.27 MPa CO and at 400 °C (mol %)
CO ₂ (g)		0
C(s)		33.55
CH ₄ (g)		21.30
H ₂ (g)		12.30
CO(g)	62.5	0.00
LiBH ₄ (s)	25	0.00
LiBO ₂ (s)		21.90
LiH(s)		0.00
MgH ₂ (s)	12.5	0.00
Mg(s)		0.00
MgO(s)		10.95
B ₂ H ₆ (g)		0.00
MgB ₂ (s)		0.00
H ₂ O(g)		0.00
O ₂ (g)		0.00
HCOO(g)		0.00
CH ₃ OH(g)		0.00
BO ₂ (g)		0.00
B(CH ₃) ₃ (g)		0.00

Table S3 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the Li-RHC-CO interactions upon heating ramp from RT to 400 °C under pure CO atmosphere.

Figure S5 – Equilibrium composition calculations for the Li-RHC-CO interactions upon heating ramp from RT to 600 °C under pure CO atmosphere for the phases showing changes.